

Full Length Article

Concomitant silanization and controlled fibronectin adsorption on S53P4 bioactive glass enhances human adipose stem cells spreading and differentiation

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ABSTRACT

Orthopedic disorders are increasing in our society due to population aging. Numerous biomaterials have been developed to support bone regeneration, however showing a strong discrepancy between *in vitro* and *in vivo* results. This has been attributed to a lack of knowledge about protein adsorption, an early step occurring after biomaterial implantation. Bioactive glass S53P4 is clinically accepted for orthopedic applications pertaining to its osteoconductive and osteogenic behavior. However, its interactions with proteins are still unclear. To better understand the impact of surface chemistry on the glass-protein interactions, bare and silanized S53P4 were placed in contact with fibronectin (fn), in static and dynamic conditions. The surfaces were characterized by zeta potential, confocal microscopy and FTIR-ATR spectroscopy. The impact of fn on the cell response was assessed by live-dead, proliferation and morphology tests, using human adipose stem cells (hASCs). Both S53P4 and silanized-S53P4 showed good cell viability. Fn was found to affect cell alignment on both bare and silanized substrates. The impact of the surface treatments on osteogenesis was evaluated studying the expression of relevant osteogenic markers (hDLX5, hRUNX2A, hOSTERIX), which was particularly promoted by the concomitant action of silanization and fn coating.

1. Introduction

In the last years an increasing number of fractures and post-surgical complications has been recorded, mainly because of the aging of the population and bacterial resistance [1]. The consequent increase in the number of surgical procedures, associated with the intrinsic risk of infection, as well as the frailty and osteoporosis in elderly patients, is negatively affecting their quality of life [2,3]. These phenomena have a significant impact also on the healthcare system, continuously increasing the associated expenses [4]. Bioactive glasses (BGs) are a promising class of biomaterials for bone tissue regeneration pertaining to their biocompatibility, bioactivity, and wide range of tailorable properties. They are characterized by osteoconductive/osteostimulative properties which make them suitable for applications in bone tissue engineering, including dentistry, fixation of small bone defects and even

treatment of osteomyelitis [5,6]. Indeed, when a BG is placed in contact with tissue and body fluids, a series of reactions occurs, beginning with a strong alkaline ion release and surface hydration leading to the formation of silanol groups (Si-OH). The exposed silanol groups polycondensate into Si-O-Si to form a silica-rich layer on the top surface of the material. This reactive layer constitutes an optimal substrate for the adsorption of calcium ions and phosphate and carbonate groups, which crystallize into hydroxyapatite/hydroxycarbonate apatite (HA/HCA). This precipitation of a ceramic phase, very close to the composition of the inorganic component of the bone extracellular matrix (ECM), strengthens the interactions between the bone and the material [7,8].

However, despite of the wide characterization of biomaterial surfaces and biological response, a meta-analysis showed a very poor correlation between material behavior *in vitro* and *in vivo* (only ~50 %), as well as between cytocompatibility and biocompatibility [9].

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Furthermore, the correlation between the expression of osteogenic markers and the osteogenesis *in vivo*, as well as between the calcium deposition *in vitro* and the osteointegration *in vivo*, is not relevant. The correlation factor was averagely below 10 %. A high percentage of false positive results was also observed, meaning that 20–45 % of the promising biomaterials successively failed *in vivo* [9]. These observations highlighted the crucial need of further studies to understand the interface between biomaterial and tissue. One of the main reasons of the discrepancy between *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies was assessed to be the lack of knowledge concerning protein adsorption, which consists in one of the first steps after BG implantation. The interaction between the material and the cells is, indeed, not direct, but mediated by proteins adsorbed on the material, either promoting or limiting cell adhesion, viability, spreading and proliferation [10].

To further improve their biological response, different treatments have been implemented on BG surfaces. BGs have been biomineralized by pre-incubation in specific buffer solutions, such as tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane (TRIS) or simulated body fluid (SBF). The pre-incubation favours the precipitation of HA/HCA phase on the top of the BG, which is beneficial at the early stage post-implantation, as this additional layer stabilizes the surfaces, reduces the potentially cytotoxic ion burst release and favours cell adhesion and proliferation [11–13]. Biomolecule surface grafting is known as an effective method to control both the surface chemistry and the biological response of the materials without altering its bulk properties. Molecules are generally grafted onto BG surface to increase its affinity with specific chemical or biological moieties. Glutaraldehyde has been proven to expose amine groups when grafted on BGs, promoting protein adsorption and consequently cell adhesion, also limiting protein denaturation phenomena once proteins adsorb on the surface [14]. Similarly, 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES) was observed to be a good coupling agent promoting BG interactions with cell adhesion factors, enhancing cell attachment and proliferation, promoting a more symmetrical cell morphology compared to the non-silanized surface [15,16]. Other aminosilanes have been also considered in literature as grafting agents, such as 3-aminopropyltrimethoxysilane, which promoted HA/HCA precipitation as spherical nanoparticles onto BG surfaces [17]. Some studies showed that adsorbing serum proteins [18] and, more specifically, fibrinogen [19] on BGs led to an increased bioactivity, enhancing the interaction between BGs and the surrounding environment and consequently HA/HCA formation for an improved *in vivo* osteointegration. Fibronectin, when adsorbed on BG surfaces, promote higher cell viability and increase cell adhesion strength [20–22].

Proteins themselves are also subjected to change when interacting with the material surface, eventually affecting their conformation and tertiary structure, and altering protein-protein interactions. A change in protein tertiary structure was reported when hemoglobin was interacting with an albumin-coated ceramic surface. This further confirms the crucial role of the adsorbed protein in mediating and determining the successive interactions between the material and the surrounding environment, fundamental to determine the fate of the implant [23]. Consequently, understanding of the phenomena occurring at the surface of the materials at the early-stage post-implantation would increase the correlation between *in vitro* and *in vivo* testing.

The aim of this study is to investigate, *in vitro*, the early-stage interactions occurring between the FDA-approved S53P4 and proteins and their impact on cell response. Fibronectin (fn) was selected as a relevant model protein, as one of the main constituents of human blood plasma playing an active role in cell adhesion. Fn was adsorbed on S53P4 bioactive glass, in static and dynamic conditions. The substrate was studied as bare and as functionalized (previously silanized with APTES) with amine groups to enhance the interactions with the protein [24,25]. The dynamic adsorption taking place *in vivo* was mimicked *in vitro*, using an electrokinetic analyzer, evaluating in real time the eventual changes in surface charge, and confocal microscopy, assessing the protein surface distributions on the substrates of interest. Fn conformation was assessed

by deconvoluting the amine band in the FTIR-ATR spectra. Dynamic and static fn adsorption was then implemented in series to estimate the protein dynamics (protein-protein interactions) over time, using zeta potential analysis and confocal microscopy. The impact of the adsorbed fn on cell response was finally investigated by assessing human adipose stem cells (hASCs) viability, proliferation, morphology, and the expression of relevant genes associated with osteogenesis (hDLX5, hRUNX2A, hOSTERIX). This study fills a crucial gap of knowledge on the relationship between surface chemistry and static vs dynamic protein adsorption. Protein dynamics and protein-protein interactions are assessed, for the first time, to the best of the authors' knowledge, at the surface of a reactive substrate. Finally, the concomitant impact of silanization and protein adsorption on hASCs behavior was also determined.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Substrates

S53P4, with a nominal composition of 53.85 mol% SiO₂, 22.66 mol% Na₂O, 21.77 mol% CaO and 1.72 mol% P₂O₅, was produced by the melt-quench method. Belgian quartz sand (SiO₂), (CaHPO₄) 2H₂O, Na₂CO₃ and CaCO₃ were utilized as precursors. The entire procedure of sample preparation is described in [26], and shortly reported in the supplementary information (SI). Discs with diameter of either 10 or 14 mm were obtained, referred to as S53P4 bare.

The samples were then silanized with 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES) as in [26], using the protocol reported in the SI. The effectiveness of S53P4 silanization was assessed by XPS as in [26]. The silanized samples are referred to as S53P4 APTES.

All the samples were stored in multi-well plates in a desiccator at room temperature and analyzed within three months.

2.2. Fibronectin

Fibronectin (fn) was extracted from human plasma prepare (Octaplas) and purified as described in [27], successively labeled with a fluorophore in order to be detected by confocal microscopy. The full protocol is reported in the SI. The fn labeled with Alpha Fluor™ 488-NHS ester (XFD488 NHS Ester, AAT BioQuest) and with Atto 565-NHS ester (#72464, Sigma Aldrich), respectively used for implementing adsorption in static (§2.2) and in dynamic conditions (§2.3), are referred to as 488-fn and 565-fn.

The solutions, 15 µg/ml in PBS, for fn adsorption (labeled and non-labeled) on BGs were optimized in previous studies [26]. A 200 µl drop of fn solution was gently placed on each disc with a pipette. The samples were then incubated for 1 hour at 37 °C. Successively, each sample was rinsed with PBS and dried under a laminar hood. The fn-coated samples, referred to as S53P4 bare fn and S53P4 APTES fn respectively, were stored in multi-well plates in a desiccator at room temperature and analyzed within 24 h.

2.3. Zeta potential analysis

Zeta potential analysis was performed on both liquid and solid samples, respectively fn solutions and S53P4 discs, to determine the charge and evaluate the electrochemical properties of the solutions and surfaces of interest.

The electrochemical analysis of liquid samples was performed using an electrophoretic analyzer (Zetasizer Nano ZS, Malvern Panalytical). The electrolyte was a 1 mM KCl solution prepared by dissolving KCl (Potassium chloride, 100 %, VWR) in ultrapure water (pH around 5.5). The lyophilized fn was rehydrated as in the SI, and further diluted with the electrolyte to reach the concentration of interest (15 µg/ml). The solution was then manually buffered with 1 M NaOH, and 0.05 M HCl if needed, to set the physiological pH (7.40±0.05). The measurement was

made in triplicate.

Zeta potential analysis of solid samples was performed using an electrokinetic analyzer (SurPASS3, Anton Paar). The electrolyte was the same as for the liquid samples analysis (1 mM KCl). Per each measurement, two samples ($\varnothing=14$ mm) were mounted inside the Adjustable Gap Cell, parallelly placing the surfaces of interest with an optimized gap of (100 ± 10) μm and inducing a controlled flow of the electrolyte between them. The physiological pH (7.40 ± 0.05) was set by automatically buffering the electrolyte before each measurement with 0.05 M NaOH buffer solution and 0.05 M HCl if needed.

Zeta potential analysis was performed both in “Zeta Potential” and “Adsorption Kinetics” mode, with two different aims.

The goal of “Zeta Potential” measurements was to compare the surface’s charge before (S53P4 bare and S53P4 APTES) and after fn adsorption (S53P4 bare fn and S53P4 APTES fn). The “Zeta Potential” measurement protocol, fully described in [28], consisted in three analysis cycles (~ 90 s each) measured at $\text{pH}=7.40\pm 0.05$ where three values of zeta potential were respectively given in output at the end of the test and successively averaged.

“Adsorption Kinetics” measurements, instead, aimed to better mimic the dynamic conditions when a biomaterial is implanted *in vivo*, with proteins flowing and eventually adsorbing at the surface [29]. Before performing the analysis, the external pressure was activated by connecting nitrogen supply to the system. The target pressure was set as 200 mbar. The “Adsorption Kinetics” consisted in two phases. During the first one, zeta potential was recorded for ~ 5 min at the surface of the samples as they are (S53P4 bare or S53P4 APTES) to determine surface charge. Successively the 565-fn solution was introduced inside the electrolyte to maintain a concentration of 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ and the zeta potential was recorded in real time (RT) for ~ 60 min. The so-obtained samples were respectively referred as S53P4 bare 565-fn RT and S53P4 APTES 565-fn RT. Zeta potential was monitored real time also on S53P4 bare and S53P4 APTES in the same conditions, without the addition of 565-fn in the electrolyte. These samples, considered as controls, are respectively referred to as S53P4 bare baseline and S53P4 APTES baseline.

“Adsorption Kinetics” measurements were also performed using the same protocol with non-labeled fn to test the eventual effect of the grafted fluorophore on zeta potential analysis. No significant differences were recorded, which is in line with the relatively low number of dyes per protein (DOL). For this reason, only the results concerning dynamic adsorption of the labeled proteins are reported.

It is well known that the measured zeta potential is a function of the solution dielectric constant. To consider the potential influence of the changes of the electrolyte properties due to the fn added to the electrolyte, a control measurement was performed. In short, after the dynamic protein adsorption, the system was rinsed for 5 min with 200 ml of hot water (twice) and 5 min with 200 ml of room temperature ultrapure water (twice), to remove any eventual trace of fn from the instrument. Successively, the surface charge of the samples onto which fn was adsorbed in dynamic, was measured in “Zeta Potential” mode using a fresh 1 M KCl as electrolyte. These samples are referred to as S53P4 bare fn RT and S53P4 APTES fn RT.

Both “Zeta Potential” and “Adsorption Kinetic” measurements were performed in triplicate.

For a deeper analysis of the adsorption process, dynamic and static fn adsorptions were performed, in series, to evaluate the overall surface stability after dynamic coating and the ability of the adsorbed fn to be eventually replaced over time by other fn molecules. First, 565-fn was adsorbed in dynamic conditions, and the substrate was gently rinsed with ultrapure water and dried under a laminar hood. Successively, 488-fn was adsorbed in static conditions on the same surface, which was then rinsed and dried. The so-obtained surfaces are referred as S53P4 bare DS and S53P4 APTES DS (Dynamic-and-Static). Non-coated surfaces (S53P4 bare, S53P4 APTES) and surfaces only coated in static (S53P4 bare 488-fn, S53P4 APTES 488-fn) and in dynamic (S53P4 bare 565-fn RT, S53P4

APTES 565-fn RT) were used as controls. All the samples were stored in multi-well plates covered by aluminum foil in a desiccator at room temperature and analyzed within 24 h by fluorescence microscopy (IX51, Olympus, Tokyo, Japan).

2.4. Fourier transform infrared-attenuated total reflectance (FTIR-ATR) spectroscopy and fn conformation

FTIR spectroscopy was performed with a PerkinElmer Spectrum One FTIR Spectrophotometer (PerkinElmer, Waltham, MA) in ATR mode. The spectra relative to the lyophilized fn and the surfaces of interest (S53P4 bare, S53P4 APTES, S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES fn) were acquired in triplicate. They were evaluated within the wavenumber range $4000\text{--}450$ cm^{-1} , with a resolution of 1 cm^{-1} , averaging 32 scans. Each spectrum was then processed with background correction and normalization to the most intense band.

The FTIR-ATR spectra of the lyophilized fn and fn-coated substrates (S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES fn) were deconvoluted in order to estimate the fn conformation and evaluate eventual variations before and after the adsorption. The deconvolution was performed with Origin 2019b 32bit. From the unprocessed spectra, the amide I band ($1715\text{--}1615$ cm^{-1}) was extracted and background-corrected [30]. Based on [30], five peaks were attributed to the fn, as shown in Table 1. The error associated to the peaks center was set to ± 10 cm^{-1} . The width of the peak was imposed to (20 ± 10) cm^{-1} and the peak area higher or equal to 0. The fitting curve was set as Gaussian and the maximum number of iterations was 2000.

The deconvolution of S53P4 bare fn amide I band is reported as an example in Fig. 1, where the original band (referred to as Absorbance), the five peaks of interest (Fit Peak 1–5) and the approximation of the band after deconvolution (Cumulative Fit Peak) are highlighted.

For each deconvoluted spectrum, the calculated center, width and area of the peaks were recorded and averaged. The contribution of each peak to the overall area was then calculated according to the following equation:

$$p(n) = \frac{A_{\text{peak}(n)}}{A_{\text{tot}}} * 100$$

where $A_{\text{peak}(n)}$ is the area under the curve of the peak n (with $n = 1, \dots, 5$ for the five peaks, respectively) and A_{tot} is the total area under the curve of the amide I band.

2.5. Assessment of biocompatibility and bioactivity of BG using cell culture

The biological characterization of the substrates of interest (S53P4 bare, S53P4 APTES, S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES fn) was implemented using human adipose stem cells (hASCs). This work was performed in agreement with the Ethics Committee of the Wellbeing services county of Pirkanmaa, Tampere, Finland (R15161). The hASCs were extracted and isolated from adipose tissue samples obtained by a female donor (age 49 years, BMI 21.4) in the context of surgical operations in the Department of Plastic Surgery, Tampere University Hospital, Finland, after the submission and the ethical approval of the donor’s written informed consent for adipose tissue samples to be used for research purposes.

Table 1
Deconvolution peaks from FTIR-ATR spectra and attributed fn conformation.

	Peak (cm^{-1})	Conformation
Peak 1	1687	β -turn
Peak 2	1668	β -turn
Peak 3	1650	Random coil
Peak 4	1636	β -sheet
Peak 5	1619	β -turn

Fig. 1. Deconvoluted amide I band obtained from the FTIR-ATR spectra of S53P4 bare fn, here reported as an example.

The biological characterization aimed to study the impact of protein adsorption on cell viability on the considered substrates, and the ability of inducing cell proliferation and spreading. Live-dead, CyQUANT and morphology tests were performed. The expression of relevant genes induced by the interaction between cells and substrates was then evaluated through gene expression tests.

2.5.1. Cell culture

The isolation and characterization of hASCs from subcutaneous adipose tissue samples was carried out as described previously by Lindroos et al. [31]. The mesenchymal origin of the isolated cells was confirmed by flow cytometric analysis (FACSaria, Becton, Dickinson and Company, Erembodegem, Belgium), performed at passage 1 to determine the expression of the surface marker [31,32]. The cell ability of adipogenic and osteogenic differentiation was respectively assessed by Oil Red O and Alizarin Red staining [33]. The mesenchymal origin was determined by the positive expression of CD73 (97 %), CD90 (99 %), and CD105 (99 %), and low or negative expression of CD14 (1 %), CD19 (0.6 %), CD45 (2.6 %), CD34 (8 %) and HLA-DR (0.9 %), further confirmed by the accumulation of lipid droplets (Oil Red O) and the deposition of mineralized matrix (Alizarin Red) [34,35].

After isolation, hASCs were cultured in T-75 polystyrene flasks (Cellstar® 75 cm² Flask, Greiner bio-one, Frickenhausen, Germany) in MEM Alpha Medium (MEM Alpha Medium (1X), Minimum Essential Medium, Gibco, Thermo Fisher) with 5 % of human serum (HS; EU Eligible, Type AB Male, Serana, Pessin, Germany) and 1 % antibiotics (10,000 units/ml penicillin, 10,000 µg/ml streptomycin, Gibco, Thermo Fisher, Life Technology Corporation, Grand Island, New York, USA).

All the experiments (live-dead, CyQUANT, morphology and gene expression tests) were implemented with the same settings. S53P4 samples, bare and silanized, were sterilized at 90 °C for 3 h. The sterilized discs were placed in sterile 48-well plates (Nunc™ Delta Surface, Thermo Scientific). A 200 µl-drop of fn solution, sterilized by 0.2 µm-filtration and diluted (15 µg/ml) in Dulbecco's Phosphate Buffered Saline (DPBS (1X), Gibco, Thermo Fisher), was gently placed on each sample to implement fn adsorption. A drop of DPBS was placed on the non-coated samples as control. The discs were then incubated for 1 h at 37 °C. In the meanwhile, hASCs were detached from the flask using 3 ml trypsin (TryPLE™ Select (1X), Gibco, Thermo Fisher) and resuspended in the culture medium (CM). The diluted fn solution and DPBS were then removed from the samples with a vacuum pump, the samples were rinsed with DPBS and dried under the laminar hood. The samples were placed into sterile 48-well plates (ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) and cells were then seeded with a plating density of 1100 cells/cm², placing 1 ml CM/well. The CM was changed every 2–3 days

and collected to be analyzed by inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES, 5110 ICP-OES, Agilent Technologies) for evaluating the ion release in the CM. The 1 ml CM extracted at each time point from each well was stored at –20 °C and then diluted in 9 ml ultrapure water after one freeze-thaw cycle, at least 24 h before the measurement. The considered elements and the relative wavelengths selected for their quantification are reported in Table 2. In the case of sodium, which was present in a substantial amount in the CM, the quantification was not possible, since in all the considered conditions this element had a higher concentration than the maximum detectable by the instrument. Therefore, sodium concentration is not reported in this context.

The cells used in this study were at passages 2–5. All the experiments were made in triplicate.

2.5.2. Live-dead

The cell viability on the substrates of interest (S53P4 bare, S53P4 APTES, S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES fn) was assessed by live-dead test, using three samples per condition. The positive control consisted in cells seeded directly at the bottom of the wells. Live-dead staining (Invitrogen, Thermo Fisher Scientific) was implemented 1, 3 and 7 days after seeding. At each time point, cells were treated with a DPBS solution containing 0.25 µM ethidium homodimer-1 (EthD-1) and 0.5 µM Calcein-AM, respectively staining dead cells red and live cells green. The samples were incubated 45 min at room temperature and rinsed with DPBS. Three areas per sample were randomly selected and imaged with a fluorescence microscope (IX51, Olympus, Tokyo, Japan).

2.5.3. CyQUANT

Cell proliferation was evaluated with CyQUANT Cell Proliferation Assay Kit (Invitrogen, Thermo Fisher Scientific) 1, 3 and 7 days after seeding. Three samples per condition (S53P4 bare, S53P4 APTES, S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES fn) were considered. The positive control consisted of cells seeded directly at the bottom of the wells. The negative controls were samples not seeded with cells. All samples and controls were treated in the same way. At each time point, cells were lysed with a solution of ultrapure water containing 0.1% vol. of triton 100x lysis buffer (Sigma-Aldrich) for 10 min and frozen at –80 °C. After one freeze-thaw cycle, three parallel volumes of 20 µl were collected from each lysate and pipetted into a black-bottom 96-well plate (Nunc®, Sigma-Aldrich). Per each, 180 µl were added of a working solution of ultrapure water containing cell lysis buffer (20X) and CyQUANT GR dye (400X). The reaction was let for 5 min and the emitted fluorescence at 480/520 nm was then immediately recorded by a multimode plate reader (VICTOR Nivo™, Perkin Elmer). The recorded fluorescence values were then averaged and the autofluorescence acquired from the negative controls at each time point was respectively subtracted.

2.5.4. Morphology

Cell morphology was studied 1, 3 and 7 days after seeding on three samples per condition (S53P4 bare, S53P4 APTES, S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES fn). The positive control were cells directly seeded at the bottom of the plastic wells. All samples and controls were treated in the same way. Briefly, at each time point, cells were rinsed with PBS, fixed with 5% vol. paraformaldehyde (PFA) for 15 min (500 µl/well) and

Table 2

The elements quantified with ICP-OES after cell tests and their relative wavelength.

Element	Wavelength (nm)
Si	251.432
Na	588.995
Ca	422.673
P	213.618
Mg	279.800

permeabilized with 0.1% vol. triton 100x lysis buffer in ultrapure water for 10 min (1 ml/well). Between fixation and permeabilization, cells were rinsed 3 times with a PBS solution containing 0.5% wt of bovine serum albumin (PBS-BSA-0.5 %). Samples were then blocked with 45 min incubation in PBS-BSA-1 % solution (1 ml/well). After blocking, the cells were incubated for 45 min in a working PBS-BSA-0.5 % solution containing 0.001% vol. of 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI) and 0.002% vol. of phalloidin-FITC, respectively, staining nuclei blue and actin filaments green. A final rinsing step was made in PBS-BSA-0.5 % (3 cycles) and ultrapure water (1 cycle). The cells were then imaged with a fluorescence microscope (IX51, Olympus, Tokyo, Japan) randomly selecting three areas per sample.

A further analysis was performed on the so-acquired images in order to evaluate how fn coating is affecting cell alignment on the substrates. The images were processed with Fiji-ImageJ-64 bit using its plug-in OrientationJ. The two evaluated channels (DAPI and phalloidin-FITC) were split, and the successive analyses were performed on the phalloidin-FITC channel to study the eventual orientation of the actin fibers. A color map showing the cell orientation on each original image was obtained setting the local window as 2 pixels and the gradient as cubic spline. The orientation angle distribution curves were also extracted imposing the same settings. To compare all the curves, the main peaks were centered in zero and the distributions normalized to the overall maximum considering all the extracted distributions. The curves relative to the same condition (S53P4 bare, S53P4 APTES, S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES fn, positive control) were averaged. The processed distribution curves were finally statistically analyzed: full width half maximum (FWHM), skewness and kurtosis were extracted from each peak. The distance between the peaks in the bimodal distributions was also calculated and expressed in degrees (°).

2.5.5. Gene expression

The effect of fn coating on the surfaces of interest (S53P4 bare, S53P4 APTES, S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES fn) was studied by gene expression tests using Reverse Transcription Quantitative Real-Time Polymerase Chain Reaction (RT-qPCR). Human DLX5, RUNX2A and OSTERIX (hDLX5, hRUNX2A, hOSTERIX) were considered as relevant osteogenic marker genes to assess the osteogenic differentiation, and the human housekeeping gene human acidic ribosomal phosphoprotein P0 (hRPLP0) was used as control [36]. hRPLP0 was selected as the reference gene, since it was shown in various studies to be stably expressed under different conditions [36–38]. The cells were seeded on four samples per condition in three parallel tests. No osteogenic medium supplements were added, in order to evaluate solely the effect caused by the substrates of interest. The samples were collected 7, 14 and 21 days after seeding. Messenger ribonucleic acid (mRNA) was then purified and transcribed into complementary desoxyribonucleic acid (cDNA) for the analysis, as described in the SI. The sequences of the used primers (Oligomer Oy, Helsinki, Finland) and the accession numbers of the relative genes are reported in Table 3.

The measurements were performed with ABI QuantStudio™ 12 K Flex System (Thermo Fisher Scientific). The data were processed using the baseline-threshold method, referencing the results to the untreated sample condition (S53P4 bare). The threshold cycles (CT) values of each

Table 3
Sequences of the primers used in RT-qPCR, and accession numbers.

Name	Sequence (5'–3')	Accession number
hRPLP0	Frw: AATCTCCAGGGGACCATT Rev: CGCTGGCTCCCACTTTGT	NM_001002
hDLX5	Frw: ACCATCCGCTCAGGAATCG Rev: CCCCCTAGGGCTGTAGTAGT	NM_005221.5
hRUNX2A	Frw: CTTCAATCGCCTCACAAACAAC Rev: TCCTCCTGGAGAAAGTTTGCA	NM_001024630.3
hOSTERIX	Frw: TGAGCTGGAGCGTCATGTG Rev: TCGGGTAAAGCGCTTGGGA	AF477981

replicate were extracted with QuantStudio™ 12 K Flex Software and the expression of each gene at each time point was normalized to the expression of hRPLP0 at the same time point, to obtain the relative gene expression (RGE) values. The normalization was made according to the following formula:

$$RGE = \frac{-\log_{10} \left(1 - \frac{1}{S_{gene}} \right) \wedge (CT_{ref-gene} - CT_{gene})}{-\log \left(-\frac{1}{S_{hRPLP0}} \right) \wedge (CT_{ref-gene} - CT_{gene})}$$

where:

- S_{gene} is the slope of the calibration curve of the considered gene (hDLX5, hRUNX2A or hOSTERIX);
- $CT_{ref-gene}$ is the CT value of the considered gene (hDLX5, hRUNX2A or hOSTERIX) calculated for the reference condition (S53P4 bare);
- CT_{gene} is the CT value of the considered gene (hDLX5, hRUNX2A or hOSTERIX) calculated for each replicate of each sample;
- S_{hRPLP0} is the slope of the calibration curve of hRPLP0;
- $CT_{ref-hRPLP0}$ is the CT value of hRPLP0 calculated for the reference condition (S53P4 bare);
- CT_{hRPLP0} is the CT value of hRPLP0 calculated for each replicate of each sample.

The RGE values were calculated for all the replicates and averaged.

2.5.6. Statistical analysis

The statistical analysis of the results was assessed with two-ways analysis of variance (ANOVA) using GraphPad Prism 9 software, setting the statistical significance as $p < 0.0001$. All the reported results are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation.

3. Results

Zeta potential in real time (RT) was recorded on bare and APTES-grafted S53P4 during the process of fn adsorption in dynamic conditions. The substrates of interest were also monitored, over time and without fn, as a control, referred to as baseline (Fig. 2(A-B)). The surface charge of the substrates before (S53P4 bare, S53P4 APTES) and after fn adsorption in static (S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES fn) and dynamic conditions (S53P4 bare fn RT, S53P4 APTES fn RT) are shown in Fig. 2 (C).

The zeta potential values measured at physiological pH were (-47.88 ± 0.76) mV for S53P4 bare, and (-17.01 ± 0.83) mV for S53P4 APTES (Fig. 2(A)), in agreement with previous observations [24,26,39]. Static fn adsorption on the bare material increased the zeta potential by ~ 40 mV, leading to less negative values as in [40]. The values recorded for all the fn-coated substrates (Fig. 2(A)) were close to the one characterizing fn solution, measured at (-5.29 ± 0.24) mV. No statistically significant differences were observed for either S53P4 APTES fn (-16.02 ± 0.47) mV or S53P4 APTES fn RT (-17.05 ± 2.20) mV. The zeta potential values recorded at the surface of S53P4 bare fn RT after dynamic adsorption was (-28.73 ± 1.69) mV, significantly more negative than the ones characterizing the bare glass coated in static conditions.

Monitoring zeta potential in real time (Fig. 2(B-C)) revealed that both the control substrates (baseline) were unstable over time, with strong fluctuations, especially on S53P4 APTES. With time an increasing trend was observed for S53P4 bare, while the trend is decreasing for S53P4 APTES. However, in both cases the zeta potential reached a plateau after 45–60 min. Fn stabilized both surfaces, attenuating the short-term fluctuations over time. Indeed, after a short transition period (around 5–10 min), zeta potential presented an almost instantaneous jump, after which the same plateau was reached (~ -8 mV), in agreement with the fn solution value (Fig. 2(A)). The difference between the

Fig. 2. (A) Zeta potential values (“Zeta potential” modality) measured at the surface of the substrates before (S53P4 bare, S53P4 APTES), after static (S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES fn) and after dynamic fn adsorption (S53P4 bare fn RT, S53P4 APTES fn RT); the black horizontal line highlights the average zeta potential value characterizing fn solution, as a reference. Zeta potential values monitored in real time (“Adsorption Kinetics” modality) during fn adsorption on (A) S53P4 bare and (B) S53P4 APTES; the substrates as they are (with no fn adsorption) were used as controls (baseline).

final zeta potential values recorded at the glass surface right after (Fig. 2 (A)) and at the end of the dynamic adsorption (Fig. 2(B-C)) was significantly lower in the case of the silanized surfaces.

To better understand the impact of the surface chemistry (bare or silanized) and the adsorption mode (static or dynamic) on the fn behavior, the surfaces of interest were imaged by fluorescence microscopy to assess the fn adsorption at the surfaces of interest. The surfaces were imaged as coated only in static (S53P4 bare 488-fn, S53P4 APTES 488-fn), only in dynamic (S53P4 bare 565-fn RT, S53P4 APTES 565-fn) and in both modes in series, dynamic followed by static (S53P4 bare DS, S53P4 APTES DS). The non-coated surfaces (S53P4 bare, S53P4 APTES) were analyzed as controls. All the images are reported in Fig. 3.

The 488-fn adsorption in static conditions was efficient on S53P4 bare 488-fn and S53P4 APTES 488-fn, as previously proven in [28]. S53P4 bare 565-fn RT (dynamic adsorption) presented a low background signal, with some more intense sporadic spots, with an intensity overall lower than for S53P4 bare 488-fn (static adsorption). The signal detected on S53P4 APTES 565-fn RT was more uniform than on the bare equivalent. However, the protein amount was observed to be lower in comparison to samples where protein were adsorbed in static conditions

(S53P4 APTES 488-fn). When fn adsorption was implemented in series, first in dynamic followed by a static adsorption, (S53P4 bare DS, S53P4 APTES DS), different responses were observed as a function of the surface treatments. S53P4 bare DS presented an intense and homogeneous signal, significantly higher than the one detected after either static or dynamic coating of bare surface. The detection of mainly green signal (488-fn), however, suggested that almost only the protein adsorbed in static was actually attached at the surface at the end of the process, while the fn previously adsorbed in dynamic condition was almost completely removed. Only few 565-fn spots were indeed detected. It was interesting to observe that sporadically, from some of the 565-fn spots, elongated agglomerations of 488-fn were departing (Fig. 3(A)). A uniform 488-fn coverage was observed on S53P4 APTES DS, covering the previously adsorbed 565-fn. 565-fn was present both as a weak background, associated to a thin coverage under the thicker 488-fn coating, and as agglomerations in strongly fluorescent spots. Also in this case, the elongated agglomerations of 488-fn were forming from some of the 565-fn spots, as on S53P4 bare DS. These structures, however, were observed to be distributed on the surface with a higher incidence. A different protein organization was also observed in certain areas of

Fig. 3. Fluorescence microscopy images acquired at the surface of (A) S53P4 bare and (B) S53P4 APTES after fn adsorption only in dynamic (S53P4 bare 565-fn RT, S53P4 APTES 565-fn RT), only in static (S53P4 bare 488-fn, S53P4 APTES 488-fn) and in dynamic and static in series (S53P4 bare DS, S53P4 APTES DS). The scalebar is 100 μm . All the images have been acquired using the same settings (2048 \times 2048 pixels, exposure time=552 ms, magnification=40x). The yellow arrows highlight the starting fn polymerization spots.

S53P4 APTES DS, showing the predominance of homogeneously distributed 565-fn and few 488-fn agglomerations in fibrils (reported in SI).

FTIR-ATR spectra were then acquired on all the fn-coated substrates (S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES fn, S53P4 bare 488-fn RT, S53P4 APTES 488-fn RT). Lyophilized fn and the non-coated substrates were also analyzed respectively as positive and negative controls. The spectra acquired from lyophilized fn (Fig. 4(A)) and the substrates coated in static conditions (S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES fn) are reported and compared to the uncoated samples (S53P4 bare, S53P4 APTES) in Fig. 4 (B-C). The substrates coated in dynamic conditions S53P4 bare 488-fn RT and S53P4 APTES 488-fn RT (not reported here) showed highly similar spectra.

Fn spectrum (Fig. 4(A)) showed bands and peaks typical of this

protein. The large band in the range 3500–3100 cm^{-1} was attributed to N–H stretching of secondary amines (amide A) [41,42] and to the O–H vibration of the water molecules [43,44]. These bands are partially overlapping with the band in 3400–3330 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the antisymmetric NH_2 stretch of primary amines. The presence of N–H bond was then further confirmed by the peak at 1538 cm^{-1} , attributed to N–H bending [45,46]. Three peaks respectively around 2954 cm^{-1} , attributed to amide B [47], and around 2871 and 2834 cm^{-1} , attributed to $-\text{CH}_3$ and $-\text{CH}_2$ groups [48], were then detected. The band centered at 1660 cm^{-1} was attributed to the stretching vibration of amide I [41], and the peak at 1545 cm^{-1} of amide II [48], both from secondary amines [41, 48]. Amide III band was detected around 1020–1060 cm^{-1} [49]. The stretching vibration of peptide C=O groups were confirmed by the presence of the peak at 1640 cm^{-1} [45,46], while the peak at 1064 cm^{-1}

Fig. 3. (continued).

was most probably due to the vibration of C—O—C group [48]. C—O—O group (around 1448 cm^{-1}), from the amino acids composing the protein, was also detected [50]. The C—N bond stretching was suggested by the presence of a peak around 1267 cm^{-1} , probably from amide III [45,50]. Four peaks around 950 , 857 , 521 and 461 cm^{-1} , due to urea bonds, were attributed to the residual impurities after fn isolation [50].

A summary of the peaks of interest is reported in Table 4.

S53P4 bare fn (Fig. 4(B)) and S53P4 APTES fn (Fig. 4(C)) presented similar spectra, where the main bands and peaks due to the presence of the adsorbed fn are present: $3500\text{--}3100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (N—H bonds), $3400\text{--}3330\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (NH_2), 2954 cm^{-1} (Amide B), 1640 cm^{-1} (peptide C = O group), 1545 cm^{-1} (amide II), 1448 cm^{-1} (C—O—O groups) and 1267 cm^{-1} (C—N bonds). S53P4 APTES spectrum (before fn adsorption), in agreement with previous studies [26], showed two pairs of small peaks around 1662 and 1621 cm^{-1} , and around 1373 and 1354 cm^{-1} , respectively due to NH_2/NH groups and C—O bond stretching [26,51–53]. The three peaks at around 990 , 867 and 740 cm^{-1} , due to amorphous structure of the silicate BG (S53P4), were observed on both the substrates before and

after fn adsorption and attributed respectively to Si—O—Si asymmetric stretching in SiO_4 units, carbonate group, and Si—O bending vibration [26,51,54].

In order to estimate the fn conformation before and after the adsorption on the substrates of interest, the amide I band, extracted from the deconvoluted FTIR-ATR spectra, corresponding to S53P4 bare fn and S53P4 APTES fn was used. This analysis was performed only on the fn-coated substrates in static conditions, since the quality of the signal on the amide I band was higher. The background noise of the amide I band of S53P4 bare 488-fn RT and S53P4 APTES 488-fn RT spectra, most probably due to a thinner fn layer, did not permit to have reproducible and unambiguous deconvolution results. The outcome of this analysis is shown in Fig. 5.

Fn, when lyophilized and not adsorbed on any substrate, was mainly characterized by an unordered structure (random coil), estimated $\sim 48\%$. β -turns constituted $\sim 32\%$ and a lower amount of β -sheets was present ($\sim 20\%$). This is in accordance with literature, demonstrating that the native fn structure consists of a mixture of compact β -structured

Fig. 4. FTIR-ATR spectra of (A) lyophilized fn, (B) S53P4 bare before and after fn adsorption, (C) S53P4 APTES before and after fn adsorption.

Table 4

Relevant peaks extracted from FTIR-ATR spectrum acquired from lyophilized fn.

Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Attributed chemical moieties/type of vibration	References
3500–3100	N-H bond from secondary amines/ stretching	[41,42]
3400–3330	NH ₂ from primary amines/ antisymmetric stretching	[45,46]
2954	Amide B	[47]
2871	—CH ₃ group	[48]
2834	—CH ₂ group	[48]
1660	Amide I/ stretching	[41]
1640	Peptide C = O group/ stretching	[45,46]
1545	Amide II/ stretching	[41,48]
1538	N-H bond/ bending	[45,46]
1448	C-O-O group	[50]
1267	C-N bond/ stretching	[45,50]
1064	C-O-C group	[48]
1060–1020	Amide III	[49]

domains and significant amount of loosely folded structures [55]. When adsorbed on S53P4, the protein tended to change its conformation with a ~30–40 % decrease in the quantity of random coils and a 2-fold increase in β -sheet content, without any significant variation in β -turns.

This trend was observed on both the S53P4 substrates, independently of the surface chemistry (bare or silanized). However, a slightly higher variation in fn conformation was recorded on S53P4 APTES fn.

The substrates of interest (S53P4 bare, S53P4 APTES, S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES fn) were then biologically characterized to evaluate the impact of fn adsorption on cell response. Fig. 6 shows the ions concentration (silicon, calcium, phosphorus, magnesium) of the hASCs CM during the cell tests. The positive control (cells seeded directly at the bottom of the wells) is reported as a reference.

Silicon (Fig. 6(A)) and calcium (Fig. 6(B)) concentrations showed an increasing trend over time. Silicon, not initially detected in the CM, reached a final concentration of around 120–140 ppm after 7 days for both the bare and silanized substrates. The positive control did not present any variation in silicon concentration. No significant difference in silicon release, between fn coated and non-coated surfaces, was observed. However, a difference between bare and APTES-treated substrates was recorded and observed to increase over time, with the silanized S53P4 having ~10 % higher concentration of silicon than the bare glass at day 7. Calcium was initially detected in the CM (~50 ppm), and a slight increase was observed in the positive control (~60 ppm) at day 7. However, the increase of the content of this element in the CM is significantly higher when the cells are in contact with S53P4, up to ~180 ppm (day 7). Similarly to what was observed with silicon, the

Fig. 5. Deconvolution analysis showing the areas (%) under the amide I bands extracted from FTIR-ATR spectra, corresponding to the relative quantity of each considered fn conformation (β -turns, random coils, β -sheets). The analysis was performed on lyophilized fn, S53P4 bare fn and S53P4 APTES fn.

calcium content was overall comparable between fn coated and non-coated surface, but significantly higher in the case of APTES-grafted surfaces. Additionally, at day 3 and day 7 a slightly lower calcium

concentration was recorded in presence of fn. Phosphorous concentration (Fig. 6(C)) showed a slightly increasing trend over time in the positive control, up to day 7 (from ~40 ppm to ~55 ppm). Despite of this, the concentration of this element was decreasing with a high slope and completely depleted (from ~40 to 0 ppm during the considered 7 days) when cells were seeded on the glass substrates, with no statistical difference between them. Magnesium concentration (Fig. 6(D)) was overall quite stable, in accordance with a previous work [56]. The variations over time were not statistically significant, as all the substrates presented similar behavior, with the initial concentration of the CM (~12 ppm) maintained over time. Only on the positive control it slightly increased up to ~15 ppm after 7 days.

The impact of adsorbed fibronectin on cells viability was assessed by live-dead test. Fig. 7 reports the fluorescence images acquired at the surface of the materials of interest at the considered time points.

Live-dead test showed only green signal (Calcein-AM), associated with live cells, on all the surfaces of interest. Qualitatively, it was observed that after 1 and 3 days the cell density on S53P4 discs was lower than on the control. At day 7 a complete confluence was observed. The results of the CyQUANT analysis, reported in Fig. 8, quantitatively confirmed these observations. A very low fluorescent signal was detected on all the substrates at day 1 with no statistical difference between the considered conditions. At day 3, a ~3–5 times higher signal (depending on the condition) was recorded. Cell proliferation was averagely lower on the silanized samples, compared to the bare ones, with no significant influence of the adsorbed fn. At day 7, the significantly higher fluorescent signal (~8–10 times compared to day 3, ~100

Fig. 6. Concentration of (A) silicon, (B) calcium, (C) phosphorous and (D) magnesium in CM evaluated by ICP-OES during S53P4 cell culture.

Fig. 7. Cell viability evaluated by live-dead test: hASCs on S53P4 bare, S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES and S53P4 APTES fn at day 1, 3 and 7 after seeding. The positive control (cells seeded directly at the bottom of the wells) is also shown. Green, live cells (Calcein-AM); red, dead cells (EthD-1). The scalebar is 200 μm .

Fig. 8. CyQUANT analysis for cell proliferation. hASCs on S53P4 bare, S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES and S53P4 APTES fn evaluated 1, 3 and 7 days after seeding. The positive control (cells seeded directly at the bottom of the wells) is also reported.

times compared to day 1) confirmed the strong proliferation between day 3 and day 7.

The morphology of the attached cells (Fig. 9) was analyzed to characterize the impact of fn coating on the cell spreading.

The cells started to attach and spread on all the substrates of interest already at day 1. The spreading was more pronounced on the silanized surfaces, where the cells were ~130 % larger than on the bare samples. A higher spreading was noticed in presence of fn, leading to an increase of ~40 % in the aspect ratio on both bare and silanized surfaces. Furthermore, a more pronounced cell alignment was qualitatively observed on fn-coated surfaces. This phenomenon was even more visible at day 3 and this tendency was maintained also at day 7, when the cells reached confluence. The tendency of cells to align in a preferential direction was further investigated. The normalized distribution curves of the cell orientation angle are reported in Fig. 10(A-E), where their statistical analysis is also shown, including the distance between the peaks (Fig. 10(F)), and the FWHM (Fig. 10(G)), skewness (Fig. 10(H)) and kurtosis of each peak (Fig. 10(I)).

Regardless of the condition (S53P4 bare, S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES, S53P4 APTES fn, positive control), the distributions at day 1 were always bimodal, showing that at the early stage hASCs tended to align in two preferential directions, which were approximately orthogonal (Fig. 10(A-E)). The orthogonality was quantitatively confirmed evaluating the distance between the two peaks, as reported in Fig. 10(F), where the angle between the two main orientations ranged from ~86 to ~102°. Over time, the cells tended then to align in a preferential direction on all the substrates and to be organized in a unimodal distribution at day 7. However, only the fn-coated surfaces (S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES fn) presented unimodal distributions already at day 3. FWHM (Fig. 10(G)) showed an analogous trend for all the conditions (S53P4 bare, S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES, S53P4 APTES fn, positive control) as a function of time, consisting in a slight but significant increase at day 3, with a successive decrease at day 7. This tendency is less pronounced in presence of fn. All the peaks were positively skewed, following a decreasing trend over time (Fig. 10(H)). The fn-coated surfaces (S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES fn) showed higher skewness values at each time point, compared to the respective non-coated ones (S53P4 bare, S53P4 APTES). The kurtosis presented, regardless of the condition, a decreasing trend (Fig. 10(I)), ranging from positive to negative values, respectively at the earlier (day 1–3) and at the later time points (day 3–7).

The impact of the adsorbed fn on gene expression was then evaluated

by RT-qPCR. The relative expression of the osteogenic markers hDLX5, hRUNX2A and hOSTERIX was evaluated 7, 14 and 21 days after hASCs were seeded on the surfaces of interest (S53P4 bare, S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES, S53P4 APTES fn). The results are shown in Fig. 11.

The relative gene expression was characterized by the same trend for all the genes (hDLX5, hRUNX2A, hOSTERIX). At day 7, no statistical difference between the conditions were observed. At day 14 an increase was observed in the case of the silanized and fn-coated surfaces. The increase was assessed to be averagely ~5 times higher in the case of hRUNX2A and ~8 times higher in the case of hDLX5 and hOSTERIX as compared to d7. The bare surfaces (S53P4 bare, S53P4 bare fn), regardless of the presence of fn, did not promote any significant increase in the relative expression of hDLX5, hRUNX2A and hOSTERIX, coherently with previous studies [36,56,57]. Successively, at day 21, all the genes were significantly downregulated with values comparable or even lower than the ones recorded at day 7. At this late stage, particularly low values were observed for hDLX5 and hRUNX2A, especially in the case of S53P4 APTES and S53P4 APTES fn.

4. Discussion

Fn had a strong stabilizing effect over S53P4, regardless of the surface conditions, either bare or silanized with APTES (Fig. 2(B-C)). Indeed, the short-term fluctuations in zeta potential characterizing the uncoated substrates, due to the electrochemical instability of the material, especially when silanized [58], were already negligible after few minutes since the start of the adsorption process, on both substrates. The fact that zeta potential tended to reach the same plateau over time regardless of the surface chemistry (around -8 mV, close to the (-5.29 ± 0.24) mV typical of the fn solution), suggested a uniform coating able to shield the initial surface charge [40].

The difference between the final zeta potential values recorded on the bare glass at the end of the dynamic adsorption (S53P4 bare 565-fn RT, Fig. 2(B)) and right after (S53P4 bare fn RT, Fig. 2(A)) was hypothesized to be due to the lower specificity of the interactions between the substrate and the protein. The weaker bonds were then presumably broken by the shear stress due to the electrolyte flow imposed during the measurement, removing some of the physisorbed fn molecules thus thinning the coating, leading to a more negative value closer to the one characterizing the non-coated substrate. The impact of shear stress on the thickness of the protein coating was also evident from Fig. 3(A). The low background signal and inhomogeneous sporadic spots on S53P4 bare 565-fn RT suggested a low amount of adsorbed protein, probably arranged into a single molecule layer, with some small aggregations concentrated in few areas at the surface. These phenomena are coherent with literature, where it was assessed that the amount of adsorbed protein is averagely lower in dynamic conditions compared to static, regardless of the imposed flow rate [59,60].

This difference in zeta potential is significantly lower in the case of the silanized surfaces (Figs. 2(C) and 2(A), respectively), further confirming the more specific and stronger interactions between the protein and the glass when APTES is grafted [59,60]. The fn coverage of S53P4 APTES 565-fn RT (Fig. 3(B)) was more uniform than on the non-silanized substrate, due to the more controlled surface chemistry with the exposed amine groups favouring protein interactions [28,39]. Indeed, due to the more specific and consequently stronger interactions, the shear stresses imposed by the flow were not able to completely break them, while also reducing the probability of fn-fn interactions [59,60]. Indeed, when adsorbed in static conditions, the protein interacting with bare or silanized surface becomes exposed to different functional groups, affecting the electrochemical properties of the surface [40,61]. In fact, as deeply discussed in previous works, the investigated substrates present a significantly different chemistry [24,26]. S53P4 bare, rich in mainly deprotonated hydroxyl groups, causing an intrinsic negative surface charge [26], probably mainly interacts with positively charged groups (NH₃⁺) of fn [28]. The less negative charge detected on

Fig. 9. Morphology of hASCs on S53P4 bare, S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES and S53P4 APTES fn evaluated 1, 3 and 7 days after seeding. The positive control (cells seeded directly at the bottom of the wells) is also shown. Green, actin (phalloidin-FITC); blue, nuclei (DAPI). The scalebar is 200 μ m.

Fig. 10. Normalized hASCs orientation angle distributions (extracted from the phalloidin-FITC channel of the morphology images) on (A) S53P4 bare, (B) S53P4 bare fn, (C) S53P4 APTES, (D) S53P4 APTES fn and (E) the positive control (cells seeded directly at the bottom of the wells), evaluated 1, 3 and 7 days after seeding. The statistical analysis of cell orientation distribution includes (F) the distance between the two peaks corresponding to the two preferential orientations in the bimodal distributions, and (G) FWHM, (H) skewness and (I) kurtosis of each detected peak. The number of FWHM, skewness and kurtosis values, being referred to each peak, could be either one or two per condition, according to the number of peaks detected in the considered distribution. For all the graphs, the same color code is used (orange for day 1, green for day 3, violet for day 7).

Fig. 10. (continued).

S53P4 bare fn suggested the presence of positive charge attributed to the fn protonated amines (Fig. 2(A)), further confirming the non-specific fn interactions with the surfaces rich in hydroxyl groups [62]. Both the positive and the negative domains of the protein are involved, leading to a non-defined fn orientation on the surface. The silanized S53P4 instead, led to a less negative charge compared to the one on the bare glass, due to APTES grafting with different conformations and exposing both neutral (deprotonated) and positively charged (protonated) amine groups [24,26,63]. The higher affinity of the surface with the protein, compared to the bare substrate, was explained by the multiple and more specific interactions between the protein and the grafted aminosilane. The less negative surface charge of the silanized substrate suggested that grafted APTES exposed a higher amount of protonated amines compared to the methyl groups (-CH₃). Consequently, it was hypothesized to interact mainly with the fn negatively charged extremity (COO⁻), while only a limited amount of positively charged extremities (NH₃⁺) were involved in the interaction with the silanized surface [26,28,63]. The slightly larger error bar can be indeed explained by the mildly higher variability in fn adsorption, with the flow removing the weakly adsorbed fn molecules from the surface. Overall, these results suggested that silanizing S53P4 led to a more homogeneous and specific fn coating on S53P4 surface, with stronger interactions between fn and substrate.

Adsorbing fn in series (first in dynamic followed by adsorption in static) again demonstrated a strong influence of the surface chemistry on the protein quantity and surface distribution. The thick and homogeneous coverage on S53P4 bare DS (Fig. 3(A)), arises from the fn

adsorbed in static (488-fn, green signal), while the one previously adsorbed in dynamic (565-fn, red signal) was almost completely removed, consisting in few sporadic spots. The authors suggest that the 565-fn spot-like agglomerations were behaving as starting points (“seeds”) of polymerization of the successively adsorbed 488-fn. The formation of small 488-fn fibrils would have been then due to the effect of the previously applied shear stress (~154 μN/mm²) during the dynamic adsorption, as forces in the order of μN at the surface were shown to induce fn polymerization in fibrils [64,65]. Furthermore, shear stresses are known to induce fn unfolding, providing additional energy to the system contributing to maintain the fibrillar state of the protein [66–69]. Vroman effect was then hypothesized, affecting fn behavior when later-arriving proteins are competing to adsorb at the surface of the material [70]. S53P4 APTES DS (Fig. 3(B)) was also characterized by a uniform and thick 488-fn coating. It was however interesting that, probably due to the more specific bonds between the protein and the surface, a homogeneous 565-fn from the molecules previously adsorbed in dynamic was still detected. This suggested that 488-fn was not completely replacing 565-fn, but it was interacting with it while coating the surface. The elongated 488-fn agglomerations were also observed on the silanized surface, but observed with a higher incidence than on the bare material most probably due to the stronger and more specific interactions between fn and APTES, slowing down the Vroman effect [24, 25]. A second scenario, less frequent but not negligible, was also observed on S53P4 APTES DS, consisting in a homogeneous coverage by 565-fn over which 488-fn was sporadically growing into fibrils (reported

Fig. 11. Relative expression of (A) hDLX5, (B) hRUNX2A and (C) hOSTERIX evaluated 7, 14 and 21 days after hASCs seeding on S53P4 bare, S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES, S53P4 APTES fn, using RPLP0 as the reference gene. Statistical analysis: $*p < 0.0001$.

in SI). The significant difference between the two described scenarios for S53P4 APTES DS was mainly explained by the fact that fn, when in solution, is generally organized in oligomeric states. Indeed, the less homogeneous coverage with the formation of agglomerations (second less frequent scenario, SI) could be due to stochastic events associated with the interactions between the oligomers and the surface [71]. A marginal role could be also played by the different possible configurations of the grafted APTES exposing either amines and methyl groups, consequently impacting on the way the fn is interacting with the functionalized substrate [24,72–74]. Specifically, in areas where APTES mainly exposed amine groups, the interface between 565-fn and the substrate was stable enough to preserve the protein coverage, interacting with the successively adsorbed 488-fn, making it prone to polymerization [64,65]. On the contrary, in the areas where APTES was mainly folded and/or exposed mainly methyl groups, the affinity with 565-fn was lower, enabling protein replacement on the surface, and the incubation at the S53P4 surface of an aqueous solution (PBS) during the implementation of the static adsorption of 488-fn probably thinned the previously adsorbed 565-fn layer [60]. This hypothesis is strengthened by previous literature, where a continuous protein release was observed from amorphous bioceramic materials when the protein-coated biomaterials were soaked in an aqueous environment [75,76], with the highest slope during the first hour of immersion [77,78], which was the duration of the implemented adsorption processes. So, overall, the

partial 565-fn release in the main scenario, leading to the thinning of the adsorbed layer, induced a homogeneous distribution of 488-fn adsorbed in static after a partial substitution of 565-fn itself. Such results could not be assigned to variations in proteins conformations. The fn conformation presented the same trend when adsorbed either on the bare or on the silanized S53P4 (Figs. 4-5). Compared to the lyophilized non-adsorbed state, fn tended to change its conformation towards a more organized molecular structure, significantly decreasing the quantity of random coils and increasing the β -sheet content, without any significant variation in β -turns. The highest variation was however recorded in the case of the APTES-grafted substrate, in line with previous studies [16,28,39] and the here presented hypothesis about the specific interactions with the substrate mediated by the grafted aminosilane [26,62]. This overall conformational change led to the hypothesis that the protein interacted with S53P4 surface maximizing the interaction sites, in this way leading to partially unfolded state, maximizing the contact area [79-81]. This hypothesis is coherent with a study demonstrating the rotation and the consequent higher packing of fn when interacting with substrates, thus exposing both hydroxyl (as in S53P4 bare) and amine groups (as in S53P4 APTES) [62]. The FnIII⁸⁻¹⁰ fragment of the adsorbed protein (Fig. 6), when in contact with a charged surface, rotates along its axis to align its dipole moment with the electric fields of the surface itself. This phenomenon would lead to a more compact fn structure when adsorbed on a charged surface [62], as the ones of interest are, as previously

assessed by zeta potential analysis (Fig. 2). Furthermore, it is known that fn tends to produce a more compact conformation in an environment with physiological pH (~7.40) and with low salt and ion content [82]. The bare glass surface, since rich in deprotonated hydroxyl groups, is prone to degradation with an increase in pH by ~0.6, upon immersion in an aqueous solution [24–26,83]. Especially in a small volume of fn solution (200 µl) for implementing static adsorption (Paragraph 2.2), the pH value, despite of the buffering PBS action, is supposed to significantly increase, leading to more alkaline conditions [83]. After silanization, instead, the S53P4 surface would be less prone to interact with the surrounding aqueous solution, mainly because of the hydroxyl groups being involved in covalent bonds with APTES. This would significantly limit the pH increase of the fn solution, which is believed to remain close to the initial one during the adsorption process [24,26]. It is known that ions in basic conditions, by electrostatically interacting with the protein, limit the number and the strength of the naturally occurring interactions between the elements 2–14 of FnIII domain and the elements 2–3 of the same domain of the other subunit (Fig. 12), which at physiological pH are prone to interact with each other for a more compact conformation of the fn molecule, [82]. It was then hypothesized that the increase in β -sheets after the adsorption on S53P4 substrates was mainly due to the increase of the previously described interactions between the two fn subunits, locally unfolding and reorganizing [79]. This would also explain why this phenomenon is stronger in case of the silanized surface, where the deviation from the originally set pH is lower, showing therefore an increase in β -sheet content [24,26].

The obtained results (decrease of unordered structure and increase of β -sheets) were confirmed by literature, showing an analogous conformational change of proteins when adsorbed on silicate BGs and, more in general, silicon-rich substrates [19,78,84]. An increase of β -sheet secondary structure was observed in various conditions after fibrinogen was adsorbed on different silica-based substrates [19,84], which was found to positively affect the cell response, overall improving the cytocompatibility of the surface [84,85]. This phenomenon was attributed to the increase in the β -sheet to β -turn ratio (bSTR) [19,84]. In the current study a slight increase of bSTR was also observed for the fn adsorbed on the silanized substrate. A bSTR of 1.11 ± 0.01 was extracted from the analysis of S53P4 APTES fn, while S53P4 bare fn was characterized by a bSTR of 1.07 ± 0.01 , both included in the range ensuring a good cytocompatibility [19,84].

The impact of fn adsorption on cell response was then evaluated including all the substrates of interest (S53P4 bare, S53P4 APTES, S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES fn). As it was observed that the fn surface distribution and conformation were comparable between static and dynamic conditions, the static adsorption was considered an appropriate model for testing the biological response. During the direct culture of hASCs, silicon (Fig. 6(A)), not initially detected in the CM, was continuously released with a significant difference, increasing over time, between the bare and silanized substrates, regardless of the eventual fn coating (~10 % higher at day 7). The release of calcium (Fig. 6(B)) was ~3 times higher in presence of the glass substrate compared to the

positive control, suggesting a strong depletion of this ions from the glass, especially when silanized. The difference in silicon and calcium release as a function of the presence of the grafted APTES at S53P4 surface was explained by the additional amount of silicon due to the grafted aminosilane, which was released over time in the CM, associated with the more reactive surface after its release, allowing a slightly stronger calcium depletion as well [26]. Differently from what was observed about silicon, fn was active in limiting calcium release, as suggested by the slightly lower calcium concentration in the CM in the case of fn-coated substrates, consistent with the previously observed stabilizing action of the protein (zeta potential, Fig. 2) [86]. Phosphorus (Fig. 6(C)) dropped to ~0 ppm at day 7 in presence of S53P4, with no significant difference between the conditions. This was attributed to the formation of the HA/HCA phase at the surface of the glass [26,56]. The stability of magnesium concentration over time in the CM when in contact with S53P4 (Fig. 6(D)), associated with its mild increase in the positive control, was explained by the tendency of this ion to be incorporated into the precipitated HA/HCA [36].

A good cell viability was assessed by live-dead (Fig. 7), as only live cells were detected on all the substrates (S53P4 bare, S53P4 APTES, S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES fn) for all the considered time points (up to day 7). A slow proliferation rate at the early stage (up to day 3), followed by a faster one at the later stage (up to day 7) leading to confluence, was qualitatively observed by live-dead and quantitatively confirmed by CyQUANT analysis (Fig. 8). The low cell proliferation during the first hours after seeding and the limited cell division until day 3 can be explained by the strong ion release characterizing S53P4 when immersed in aqueous solutions, slowing the process of adhesion at the surface [57,83]. This phenomenon is attributed to the burst of ions released upon immersion in the culture medium. However, at longer culturing time, after the first burst ion release, the ion exchange rate decreased to reach a steady state [24]. Along with the formation of the silica gel and the precipitation of the reactive layer, cells behavior was positively influenced, leading to the migration of the cells from the polystyrene to the S53P4 substrates and to a fast proliferation on them. At day 7 the confluence was reached in all the conditions, with a complete coverage of the substrates [56,57].

Despite of the relatively low proliferation rate for up to day 3, all cells showed an appropriate spread morphology on all the substrates at each time point (Fig. 9). The spreading was particularly enhanced by silanization, with ~130 % larger cells than on the bare material, and by fn coating, with ~40 % higher aspect ratio compared to the uncoated substrates. It was consequently hypothesized that these two conditions were boosting the formation of focal adhesions [16]. Fn was also responsible for an earlier and more pronounced cell alignment, promoting cells to self-orient in a preferential direction. This fn-driven phenomenon, already observed in literature associated with a more elongated and symmetrical cell shape [16,87], was further confirmed by a quantitative analysis by extracting the cell distribution curves as a function of their orientation angle, and evaluating the distance between the peaks, and the FWHM, skewness and kurtosis of each peak. At day 1

Fig. 12. Schematic fn structure. The main elements and binding sites are highlighted. (Adapted from [28]).

all the distributions were bimodal, with the cells orienting orthogonally and tending to align to each other over time, reaching a unimodal distribution by day 7 (Fig. 10(A-F)). It was however interesting to observe that the fn-coated substrates already reached the unimodal distribution at day 3, suggesting that fn boosted the orientation in a single preferential direction, anticipating the overall cell alignment, regardless of the surface chemistry (bare or silanized) [16,87]. Cell alignment was further boosted by fn even at day 7, as suggested by the lower FWHM values (Fig. 10(G)) at day 3–7, compared to the ones recorded for the uncoated substrates [62,88]. The different cell orientation kinetics based on the presence or the absence of the adsorbed fn at the surface of the material could be explained by the exposure of Arg–Gly–Asp (RGD) domains by the protein. Indeed, it was demonstrated that, when adsorbed on either hydrophilic (as all the substrates considered in this study) or positively charged surfaces (as the silanized surfaces exposing protonated amines), fn structure rotates to expose its cell-binding sites present in FnIII fragment (Fig. 12) [62]. FnIII fragment exposes both RGD and Pro–His–Ser–Arg–Asn (PHSRN) domains, which respectively enhance affinity to cells and undergo a controlled unfolding process, increasing the elasticity of the protein, inducing a 7-fold stretch of the site and consequently promoting cell binding [62,88,89]. The authors believe that the presence of the adsorbed fn at S53P4 surface could in this way impact on cell adhesion process, leading to a faster and more accentuated one-direction cell alignment on fn-coated surfaces. The positive skewness of all the distribution peaks (Fig. 10(H)) was attributed to a slightly asymmetrical cell distribution, and its decreasing trend was explained by the tendency to a more symmetrical alignment over time. This was observed for all the conditions (S53P4 bare, S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES, S53P4 APTES fn, positive control). The fn-coated substrates always showed an averagely higher skewness of the peaks, due to the spontaneous cell tendency to symmetrically align with a slight divergence induced by the presence of the adsorbed protein at the surface. The kurtosis of the peaks (Fig. 10(I)) had also a decreasing trend: at day 1–3, the distributions were narrower than the theoretical normal distribution (positive values) and successively, at day 3–7, tended to spread with a larger width compared to the Gaussian distribution (negative values). This is in line with the cell spreading occurring over time, already observed in the morphology analysis (Fig. 9).

The relative expression of relevant osteogenic markers (hDLX5, hRUNX2A, hOSTERIX) was evaluated by RT-qPCR, showing a significant upregulation of all the genes at day 14 on S53P4 APTES and S53P4 APTES fn. The higher upregulation of hOSTERIX compared to hDLX5 and hRUNX2A was probably due to the relatively late-stage expression characterizing this gene, while hDLX5 and hRUNX2A are known to be upregulated at earlier stages (up to day 14) [90–92]. Coherently with previous studies, no significant variation in the expression of these genes was recorded on the bare surface, regardless of the presence of fn [36,56,57]. This led to hypothesis that silanization itself was boosting the expression of the considered osteogenic markers, and this phenomenon was further promoted by fn coating, especially in the case of hOSTERIX [90–92]. The downregulation at day 21 of all the markers, with values comparable or lower than the ones recorded at day 7, was explained by the earlier expression of the genes (especially hDLX5 and hRUNX2A), further promoted by the reached confluence [90–92]. Specifically, hDLX5 is the first gene out of the considered ones to be eventually activated by the chemical stimuli from the surrounding environment [92,93]. hRUNX2A can be activated being bound by specific proteins (e. g., hDLX5 protein) in its C-terminus, consequently upregulating the genes promoting the production of other protein, such as osteocalcin, osteopontin, collagen I and bone sialoprotein [90–93]. The activation of hRUNX2A also enhances the regulation of hOSTERIX [94]. It is then reasonable to conclude that all the substrates considered in the current studies (S53P4 bare, S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES, S53P4 APTES fn) were able to promote the expression of osteogenic marker genes (hDLX5, hRUNX2A, hOSTERIX) inducing the described cascade of gene activation. Particularly, the silanized S53P4 surfaces (with and without fn)

seemed to enhance the gene expression of the osteogenic biomarkers more than the non-silanized ones. It was therefore hypothesized that the initial homogeneous and stable fn coating and the tight attachment of serum proteins induced by the grafted APTES at the surface of the material promoted the differentiation towards a bone genotype [28].

5. Conclusions

The silicate BG S53P4, FDA-approved and clinically available, was silanized with APTES to increase the control over the surface chemistry and protein adsorption. Both the silanized and bare surfaces were coated with the model protein fn in dynamic conditions to mimic the dynamic adsorption occurring *in vivo*. The bare material was less efficiently coated by the protein, with a less homogeneous and thinner layer, due to the non-specific interactions between the protein and the substrate. Conversely, silanization promoted a uniform fn coverage of S53P4, explained by the specific interactions mediated by the exposed amine groups of the grafted APTES. However, regardless the surface was bare or silanized, the adsorbed fn was homogeneous enough to be always able to shield the initial surface charge of the material, and expose the charge of the fn. Fibrillogenesis was also observed for all the conditions, promoted by the continuous shear stress induced by the fn solution flow at the surface of the material during the adsorption process. Surface adherence had an influence on fn secondary structure, increasing the amount of β -sheets and reducing the quantity of random coils, as compared to the non-adsorbed lyophilized protein. The cells exhibited a good viability on all the substrates (S53P4 bare, S53P4 bare fn, S53P4 APTES, S53P4 APTES fn), with an analogous proliferation trend, lower at the early stage (up to day 3) and faster at the later stages, reaching the confluence at day 7. While cells stayed mostly poorly spread in fn-grafted bare S53P4 at day 1, they showed a well spread morphology at all the later time points and throughout the whole study period in the other samples. The presence of fn at the surface of the material promoted cell alignment in a preferential direction, leading to a unimodal distribution already at day 3. Further culturing increased the variance in the directionality, likely because the cell culture become confluent already at day 7. Fn adsorption did not lead to significant impact on the expression of osteogenic marker genes (hDLX5, hRUNX2A, hOSTERIX). The considered genes were expressed at a comparable level at day 7 and day 21, while a significant upregulation was observed at day 14, especially in the case of the silanized material (with and without adsorbed fn). This suggested a beneficial effect of silanization in promoting osteogenesis, likely via tighter serum protein attachment on silanized BGs.

The promising impact of silanization on protein adsorption and osteogenesis will be further studied when associated with the adsorption of other relevant serum proteins, such as albumin, immunoglobulin G and fibrinogen, in a more complex biomimetic multi-protein system. Moreover, the here assessed observations need to be confirmed in the future by *in vivo* studies to demonstrate the effectiveness of the developed *in vitro* model to simulate protein adsorption.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Virginia Alessandra Gobbo: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Amel Houaoui:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Kimiya Tajik:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Vesa P. Hytönen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Susanna Miettinen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition. **Jonathan Massera:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Virginia Alessandra Gobbo reports financial support was provided by Tampere University. Jonathan Massera reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe. Vesa Pekka Hytonen reports financial support was provided by Research Council of Finland. Vesa Pekka Hytonen reports financial support was provided by Sigrid Jusélius Foundation. Vesa Pekka Hytonen reports financial support was provided by Cancer Foundation Finland. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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Supplementary materials

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